

NORMAL ALUMINIUM CHROMATE.

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A method for the preparation of normal aluminium chromate has been reported and different properties of this substance thoroughly investigated.

From a study of the literature it appears that attempts by various workers to prepare normal aluminium chromate gave only basic chromates of variable composition such as $2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, \text{CrO}_3, 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$; $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, \text{CrO}_3, 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, etc. all of which are insoluble in water. Comparatively recent literature on the subject also furnishes conflicting reports about the composition and constitution of this substance (*cf.* Calcagni, *Gazzetta*, 1925, 35, 396; Bianc, *Ann. Chim. phys.*, 1926, x, 6, 182; Charrion, *J. chim. phys.*, 1926, 23, 621; Briggs, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 242).

Thus it appears that normal aluminium chromate has probably not yet been known. While most of the above workers have been able to obtain an insoluble substance, none has yet obtained any aluminium chromate which is soluble in water. So it is thought that the investigation into the preparation and properties of normal aluminium chromate would be interesting.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An excess of freshly prepared solid silver chromate with pure crystalline aluminium chloride were triturated in a mortar with the least possible quantity of ice-cold water. It was kept in a frigidaire for 3 days and the deep brown solution was decanted and filtered through quantitative filter paper twice. The solution was tested free from Ag^+ and Cl^- ions. It was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator containing concentrated sulphuric acid and kept in the frigidaire. A deep brown substance was obtained.

Both the brown solution and the solid were analysed. The chromate was determined iodometrically. A known weight of the substance was strongly heated till the weight of the mixture of the oxides was constant and also the weight of aluminium calculated from this. The ratio between $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3$ was 1 : 3 in both the cases.

The solid was triturated with ice-cold glacial acetic acid several times. It was then dried in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid

and solid caustic potash in the frigidaire till a constant weight was obtained. The dry solid was then analysed as above. Results of analysis showed that $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 : \text{CrO}_3 : \text{H}_2\text{O}$ to be 1:3.004:5.005. This indicates that the formula of the compound is probably $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3, 3\text{CrO}_3, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ i.e. $\text{Al}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3, 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Action of Heat.—By heating a known weight of the substance to a constant weight, a mixture of Al_2O_3 and Cr_2O_3 was obtained which contributed to the extent of 66.61% of the total weight of the substance. If, however, the composition of the substance be assumed as given above and if the reaction takes place according to the equation

the mixture of the oxides should amount to 67.01%.

Measurement of Molecular Conductivity.—The following figures show that the values for molecular conductivity of the substance at different dilutions (at 28°) are comparable to those of AlCl_3 and $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ at 25°. This suggests that most probably the compound in solution electrolytically dissociates into five ions.

TABLE I.

Dilution (litres)	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	4096	8192
Mol. condy. (μ_p)	—	298.87	340.23	364.76	398.12	425.35	466.23	491.16	510.89
Mol. condy. of AlCl_3	—	—	342.00	371.00	393.00	413.00	—	—	—
Mol. condy. of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$	158.01	—	219.04	—	301.01	—	425.05	514.06	—

Measurement of p_H .—A solution of the substance ($N/15$) was prepared by dissolving 1/90th of its formula weight per litre of solution. p_H values of this solution as well as those of an equivalent solution of chromic acid, AlCl_3 and $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ and also of a $N/15$ solution of H_2SO_4 and CrCl_3 were determined at the room temperature with glass electrode. Results given below indicate the constitution of the substance to be similar to that of $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$.

TABLE II.

Substance	$N/10\text{CrCl}_3$	$N/15\text{H}_2\text{SO}_4$	$N/15\text{H}_2\text{CrO}_4$	$N/15\text{AlCl}_3$	$N/15$ Substance	$N/15\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$
p_H ...	1.25	1.45	1.82	3.71	3.68	3.41

Degree of Hydrolysis.—It was calculated from the p_H value of the $N/15$ solution and was found to be 1.88×10^{-2} .

Chemical Properties.—The substance reacts acid to litmus. With NH_4OH and NaOH it produces a white gelatinous precipitate soluble in excess of NaOH . Concentrated AgNO_3 solution gave a red precipitate soluble in HNO_3 , while a dilute solution produced a black precipitate. Both BaCl_2 and lead acetate gave yellow precipitate soluble in HNO_3 in the case of barium salt. While K_2CrO_4 produced a brownish gelatinous precipitate soluble in acids, $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ gave no precipitate. Mercuric chloride produced a white precipitate and H_2O_2 turned the solution deep violet which gradually turned brown.

These experiments evidently indicate that the compound formed is probably the normal aluminium chromate, $\text{Al}_2(\text{CrO}_4)_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

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Received August 7, 1941.
